

1 From zero to infinity: minimum to maximum diversity
2 of the planet by spatio-parametric Rao's quadratic
3 entropy

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6 **Abstract**

7 **Aim:** The majority of work done to gather information on Earth diversity has been
8 carried out by in-situ data, with known issues related to epistemology (e.g., species
9 determination and taxonomy), spatial uncertainty, logistics (time and costs), among
10 others. An alternative way to gather information about spatial ecosystem variability
11 is the use of satellite remote sensing. It works as a powerful tool for attaining rapid
12 and standardized information. Several metrics used to calculate remotely sensed
13 diversity of ecosystems are based on Shannon's Information Theory, namely on the
14 differences in relative abundance of pixel reflectances in a certain area. Additional
15 metrics like the Rao's quadratic entropy allow the use of spectral distance beside
16 abundance, but they are point descriptors of diversity, namely they can account
17 only for a part of the whole diversity continuum. The aim of this paper is thus to
18 generalize the Rao's quadratic entropy by proposing its parameterization for the
19 first time.

20 **Innovation:** The parametric Rao's quadratic entropy, coded in R, i) allows to
21 represent the whole continuum of potential diversity indices in one formula, and ii)
22 starting from the Rao's quadratic entropy, allows to explicitly make use of distances
23 among pixel reflectance values, together with relative abundances.

24 **Main conclusions:** The proposed unifying measure is an integration between
25 abundance- and distance-based algorithms to map the continuum of diversity given
26 a satellite image at any spatial scale. Being part of the `rasterdiv` R package, the
27 proposed method is expected to ensure high robustness and reproducibility.

28 *Keywords:* biodiversity; ecological informatics; modelling; remote sensing; satellite
29 imagery.

30

1 Introduction

Since Alexander von Humboldt (1769-1859), the spatial component of nature has played a relevant role in natural science. In the development of theoretical and empirical models in ecology, spatial structure represents a key concept to allow scientists to link ecological patterns to the generating processes and to the functional networking among organisms (Borcard & Legendre, 2002). The majority of the work done to gather information about Earth diversity has been carried out by in-situ data, with known issues related to epistemology (e.g., species determination and taxonomy), spatial uncertainty, logistics (time and costs), among others (Rocchini et al., 2011).

Using satellite remote sensing can at least help attaining rapid and standardized information about Earth diversity (Gillespie, 2005; Rocchini et al., 2005). Furthermore, remote sensing can also be used to monitor some ecosystem functions and parameters such as temperatures, precipitation, photosynthesis, vegetation biomass production and precipitation (Schimel et al., 2019; Zellweger et al., 2019) that can be useful to define the different niches of in-situ species, following Goodall (1970) ideas, who envisaged future diversity measures as those based on niche theory (Hutchinson, 1959). The free access to remote sensing data (see Zellweger et al., 2019) has opened new ways to study ecosystem diversity and biodiversity issues (Rocchini et al., 2013). The spectral data related to pixels, as operational geographical units, are descriptions of pieces of land that allow us to define a new kind of Earth “diversity”, which may complement in-situ biodiversity measurement (Hernandez-Stefanoni et al., 2012).

Diversity varies with area, thus investigating multiple spatial grains, until wide extents, is important to effectively monitor spatial diversity change in space and time (MacArthur et al., 1966). This is especially true in macroecology, where the primary aim

55 is to model large-scale spatial patterns to infer the ecological processes which generated
56 them, particularly considering the recent effect of global changes worldwide (Hobohm et
57 al., 2019). In order to determine the horizontal distribution of diversity within a satellite
58 image (i.e. which areas within the image are more diverse than others), diversity indices
59 are usually spatially referenced by calculating the index within a moving window.

60 Several metrics that measure diversity from satellites rely on the Shannon’s theory of
61 entropy (Shannon, 1948), with diversity being measured as $H = -\sum_{i=1}^N p_i \log p_i$, where
62 p_i is the proportion of the i -th pixel value (e.g., digital number, DN) found within a
63 moving window containing N pixels. Shannon’s H basically summarizes the partition of
64 abundances (*sensu* Whittaker, 1965) by taking into account both relative abundance and
65 richness of DNs (Figure 1).

66 However, Shannon’s entropy is a point descriptor of (remotely sensed) diversity. As
67 such, it shows only one part of the whole potential diversity spectrum at a glance. The
68 use of generalized entropies has been advocated to face such problem. In this case, one
69 single formula represents a parameterized version of a diversity index, thus providing a
70 continuum of potential diversity indices. In the context of the measurement of diversity,
71 the Rényi (1970) parametric entropy

$$H_\alpha = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \sum_{i=1}^N p_i^\alpha \quad (1)$$

72

73 with $0 \leq \alpha \leq \infty$ represents a powerful tool to account for the continuum of diversity
74 (Figure 1).

75 One particularly convenient property of H_α is that by varying the parameter α there
76 is a continuum of possible diversity measures, which differ in their sensitivity to rare and

77 abundant DNs, becoming increasingly dominated by the most common DNs for increasing
 78 values of α . Note that for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, H_1 equals the Shannon’s entropy. A similar formulation
 79 was then proposed by Hill (1973) who expressed parametric diversity as the “numbers
 80 equivalent” of Rényi generalized entropy (Appendix S1).

81 Rényi (and Hill) parametric functions summarize diversity by taking into account the
 82 pixel values of a satellite image and their relative abundances. However, they do not allow
 83 to explicitly consider the differences among these values. As an example, two arrays of
 84 9 pixels with maximum richness and evenness (i.e. both containing 9 different DNs with
 85 relative abundances $p_i = \frac{1}{9}$) but differing in their values will attain the same Shannon
 86 diversity irrespective of the values of the DNs in both arrays.

87 By introducing a distance parameter d_{ij} among each pair of values i and j , Rao’s
 88 quadratic entropy (Rao , 1982)

$$Q = \sum_{i,j=1}^N p_i p_j d_{ij} \quad (2)$$

89

90 explicitly considers the differences among the pixel values in the calculation of diversity
 91 (Figure 1). Hence, two different pixels with values [2,3] will attain a lower diversity with
 92 respect to two pixels with values [0,100]. For instance, to make an ecological parallel, this
 93 is somewhat similar to the phylogenetic distance between two species: the values [2,3]
 94 would be equivalent to two sister species closely related on the tree of life while [1,100]
 95 would be equivalent to two very distant species on the tree of life.

96 The aim of this paper is thus to propose, for the first time, a parameterization of
 97 Rao’s quadratic entropy in order to provide a generalized entropy which accounts for
 98 both relative abundances and distances among pixel values. The proposed approach is

99 now part of the `rasterdiv` R package, a package dedicated to diversity measures of
100 spatial matrices, increasing its capability to discern among different diversity measures
101 by a single formula.

102 2 Spatio-parametric Rao's quadratic entropy

103 Inter-pixel spectral distances are directly related to landscape heterogeneity and they
104 are capable of describing species habitats, starting with a satellite image (Rocchini et al.,
105 2005). A satellite image can be viewed as a matrix of numbers describing Earth reflectance
106 in different dimensions stored as pixels. A sensor per each light wavelength records the
107 reflectance of a certain object in that wavelength which are stored into numbers in a
108 certain range (e.g., digital numbers in 8 bits, ranging from 0 to 255). In general, the
109 higher the variability in the spectral space defined by the pixel reflectance values, the
110 higher the diversity of the ecosystem under study.

111 Consider a window of N pixels moving across the whole image to calculate a diversity
112 index. Let i and j be two pixels randomly chosen with repetition within the moving
113 window. Let d_{ij} be a symmetric measure of the (multi)spectral distance between i and j
114 such that $d_{ij} = d_{ji}$ and $d_{ii} = 0$. Rao's Q (Rao , 1982) is defined as:

$$Q = \sum_{i,j=1}^N p_i p_j d_{ij} = \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N} d_{ij} \quad (3)$$

115

116 Therefore, Q measures the expected (i.e. mean) distance between two randomly
117 chosen pixels and $\frac{1}{N}$ is the probability to extract each pixel. Note that, unlike H_α or
118 K_α the calculation of Rao's quadratic entropy is not limited to single bands but can

119 be extended to multispectral systems of any dimension. For the connection between
 120 quadratic entropy and variance, see Rocchini et al. (2019).

121 A more direct approach for developing a parametric version of quadratic entropy stems
 122 from the work of Guiasu & Guiasu (2011). Let $\omega_{ij} = \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N}$ be the combined probability
 123 of selecting pixels i and j in this order. Guiasu & Guiasu (2011) noted that Rao's Q can
 124 be expressed as a linear function of the combined probabilities of all pairs of pixels:

$$Q = \sum_{i,j=1}^N \omega_{ij} d_{ij} = \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N} d_{ij} = \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N^2} d_{ij} \quad (4)$$

125

126 In practice, Rao's Q is the arithmetic mean of the distances d_{ij} between all pairs of
 127 pixels i and j . Hence, in order to implement a parametric version of Rao's Q , it seems
 128 natural to substitute the arithmetic mean in Equation 4 with a generalized mean (Hardy
 129 et al., 1952):

$$Q_\alpha = \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^N \omega_{ij} d_{ij}^\alpha \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} = \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N^2} d_{ij}^\alpha \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (5)$$

130

131 This operation connects Q_α with other diversity metrics that are expressed as gener-
 132 alized means, such as Hill's (Hill, 1973) or Jost's (Jost, 2006) numbers (Appendix S1)
 133 equivalents (see also Leinster & Cobbold, 2012).

134 The Rao's Q , viewed as an arithmetic mean, is one of all the possible means in its
 135 generalized form Q_α :

$$Q_\alpha = \begin{cases} \alpha \rightarrow 0, Q_0 = \sqrt[N^2]{\prod_{i,j=1}^N d_{ij}} & \text{geometric} \\ \alpha = 1, Q_1 = Q = \sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N^2} d_{ij} & \text{arithmetic} \\ \alpha = 2, Q_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N^2} d_{ij}^2} & \text{quadratic} \\ \alpha = 3, Q_3 = \sqrt[3]{\sum_{i,j=1}^N \frac{1}{N^2} d_{ij}^3} & \text{cubic} \\ \alpha \rightarrow \infty, Q_{\alpha \rightarrow \infty} = \max d_{ij} & \text{max}_d \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

136

137 The mathematical proof that i) for $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ Q_0 corresponds to the geometric mean,
138 and ii) for $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$ Q_∞ corresponds to the maximum distance between pixel values pairs
139 is provided in Appendix S1.

140 Each generalized mean always lies between the smallest and largest of its values.
141 Increasing the parameter α will increase the weight of the highest values of d_{ij} , thus
142 providing a continuum of potential diversity indices (Figure 1).

143 3 The algorithm

Starting from a satellite image, a spatial moving window might be used to make the calculation on predefined extents of analysis. The grain (*sensu* Dungan et al., 2002) will be the resolution of the image while the extent of analysis will be the size of the moving window (see Figure S1 in Appendix S2). The calculation is based on a distance matrix

of type:

$$M_d = \begin{pmatrix} d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_1, \lambda_n} \\ d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_2, \lambda_n} \\ d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_3, \lambda_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_1} & d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_2} & d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_3} & \cdots & d_{\lambda_n, \lambda_n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

144

145 among all the potential pairs of pixels inside the moving window. The diagonal terms
 146 of the matrix (which equal zero) will have no effect for $\alpha > 0$ (Equation 6), since they
 147 would enter the \sum term. On the contrary, for $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, they would enter the \prod term by
 148 nullifying Q_0 .

149 We coded the proposed parameterization of Rao's quadratic entropy as an R function,
 150 implementing the previously developed `rasterdiv` package (Marcantonio et al. (2020),
 151 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv>). The calculation of different Q_α
 152 by automatically changing the range of potential α values is done by the function `paRao`,
 153 as:

```
154 > paRao(x, alpha=c(0:4, Inf), method="classic", 1
155   dist_m="euclidean", window=9, na.tolerance=0.5, simplify=3,
156   np=8, cluster.type="SOCK", diag=TRUE) 3
```

157 where `x` is the input dataset which can be a `RasterLayer` or a matrix class object,
 158 `alpha` is the α parameter of Equation 5, which can be a single value or a vector of integers.
 159 In the example above, α is a vector of integers ranging from 0 to 4, plus `Inf`, which in
 160 the R language is a reserved word representing positive infinity ($\alpha \rightarrow \infty$). The option
 161 `method` decides if `paRao` is calculated with 1 single layer (`classic`) or with more than
 162 one layer (`multidimension`). With `method="multidimension"` then `x` must be a list of

163 objects. `dist.m` is the type of distance considered in the calculation of the index, and can
164 be set to any distance class implemented in the R package `proxy`, such as "euclidean",
165 "canberra" or "manhattan". Moreover, `dist.m` can also be an user-defined matrix of
166 distances. However, if `method` is set to "classic" (unidimensional paRao) all distance
167 types reduce to the Euclidean distance. The argument `window` is the side length in cells
168 of the moving window (in this case set to 9), whereas `na.tolerance` is the proportion
169 (0-1) of NA's cell allowed in a moving window: if the proportion of NA's cells in a moving
170 window exceeds `na.tolerance` then the value of the moving window central pixel will
171 be NA. The option `simplify` allows to reduce the number of decimal places to ease
172 the calculation by reducing the number of numerical categories, i.e., if `simplify=3` only
173 the first three digits of data will be considered for the calculation of the index. `np` is
174 the number of parallel processes used in the calculation. If `np>1` then the `doParallel`
175 package will be called for parallel calculation, and `cluster.type` will indicate the type
176 of cluster to be opened (default is "SOCK", "MPI" and "FORK" are the alternatives). The
177 `diag` argument refers to the diagonal term of Equation 7. It will have no effect on the
178 function for $\alpha > 0$, while it will nullify the value of Q_α if set to TRUE, as previously
179 explained in Equation 7.

180 In the next section we provide an ecological example of the application of the spatio-
181 parametric Rao's Q, done at regional scale to allow a comparison with in-situ data on
182 species diversity. Appendix S2 provides an example at worldwide spatial scale.

183 **3.1 Study case: the diversity of vegetation greenness and the** 184 **ecoregions of California**

185 A comparison between in-situ and remotely sensed diversity at worldwide scale might
186 be difficult due to known biases in e.g. sampling effort, taxonomies, spatial uncertainty
187 (Rocchini et al., 2017). Hence, we decided to calculate the parametric Rao's Q index on
188 a NDVI raster layer of California (USA) to be compared with data in the field on native
189 plant species diversity provided in Thornhill et al. (2017) from Baldwin et al. (2017).
190 We chose California as a case study due to its high ecological diversity as well as to the
191 availability of plant species field-data for this region.

192 In practice, we aimed at visualizing and describing differences in both diversity and
193 structure of vegetation for the state of California, USA. First, an NDVI raster layer
194 was derived from Copernicus Sentinel-2 data (European Space Agency, reference period:
195 January 2017 to July 2018) and processed through Google Earth Engine to filter out cloud
196 cover, select the greenest pixel of the time series and resample at 100 m pixel resolution.
197 Then, the `paRao` R function was used to derive the Rao's Q index, considering both the
198 original formulation of the Rao's Q ($\alpha = 1$, Equation 6) and the formulation with $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$
199 maximizing β -diversity (Appendix S2), with a moving window of 9x9 pixels.

200 A map of plant species richness was derived relying on the potential distribution
201 range of 5,222 native California vascular plants modelled by Thornhill et al. (2017) and
202 used to report alpha-diversity (plant species richness per pixel), whereas a vector map of
203 the ecoregions of California (level III; from the United States Environmental Protection
204 Agency) was used to identify beta-diversity. In Figure 2, we showed NDVI, the Rao's Q
205 indices with $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$ and native plant species richness, reporting the boundaries
206 of the different ecoregions for California. This comparison revealed macro-ecological and

207 bio-geographical patterns which can be better interpreted considering the information
208 condensed in the Rao's Q index (Figure 3). We focused on five important ecoregions,
209 which were used in Figure 2 and in the boxplots of Figure 3 to discuss the most evident
210 ecological patterns.

211 Overall, the Rao's Q index matched native plant species diversity in areas character-
212 ized by a lower human impact, such as in the northwest and southeast portions of the
213 state. The "Cascades" (CAS) and "Klamath Mountains" (KM) ecoregions are charac-
214 terized by highly dissected ridges, foothills, and valleys and host a very diverse flora, rich
215 in endemic and relic species (Griffith et al., 2016). Rao's Q was the highest in these two
216 areas (apart for the agricultural and urbanized areas described later), despite moderate
217 NDVI values (Figures 2 and 3). The low mountains covered by highly productive, rain-
218 drenched evergreen forests composing the "Coast Range" (CR) ecoregion showed lower
219 plant diversity and Rao's Q, despite very high NDVI values. By contrast, the dry and
220 warm "Mohave basin and range" (MBR) is characterized by broad basins and scattered
221 mountains and showed low NDVI, Rao's Q and plant species richness.

222 On the other hand, Rao's Q performed poorly when compared with native plant
223 species richness in agricultural and developed lands with a high productivity (i.e., high
224 NDVI) and heterogeneity. This is the case of the "California Central Valley" (CCV)
225 region, which is composed of flat, urbanized and intensively farmed plains. The exten-
226 sive presence of irrigated crops intersected with urbanized areas caused medium to high
227 NDVI values and an apparently high Rao's Q diversity, but a low native species richness,
228 especially in the drier southern portion of the valley.

229 Passing from the pure Rao's Q index ($\alpha=1$) to its parameterization with $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$
230 helped to increase the discrimination among areas, due to the fact that when $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$

231 the Rao's Q corresponds to the maximum distance (β -diversity) among pixel values in a
232 site. Very similar gradients of the spatial heterogeneity of California (including BIOMOD
233 variables, NDVI, elevation) as well as environmental DNA (eDNA) data are found in Lin
234 et al. (2020).

235 4 Discussion

236 In this paper, we provided a straightforward solution to: i) account for distances in an
237 Information Theory based metric, and ii) provide a generalized formula in order to avoid
238 point description and account for the continuum of diversity. Diversity can be represented
239 by different dimensions (Nakamura et al., 2020). Considering one single metric to account
240 for the whole continuum of diversity metrics might be a powerful addition to the main
241 framework. On the contrary, fragmenting the concept of diversity when trying to capture
242 single aspects of the whole spectrum could be counterproductive.

243 The proposed unifying measure succeeded to integrate abundance- and distance-based
244 algorithms over a wide variety of diversity metrics. We demonstrated that such integra-
245 tion is not only theoretical but also applicable to real spatial data, considering several
246 dimensions of diversity at the same time. Being part of the `rasterdiv` R package, the
247 proposed method is expected to ensure high robustness and reproducibility.

248 Remote sensing is obviously not a panacea for all the organismic based diversities like
249 taxonomic-, functional-, genetic-diversity but it can represent an important exploratory
250 tool to detect diversity hotspots and their changes in space and time at the ecosystem
251 level. First of all, it measures heterogeneity of the environment with indirect links to
252 the biodiversity of both plant and animal taxa, but also with potential discrepancies
253 with species diversity, as in the presented case study of the native plant species diversity

254 of California. This said, depending on the complexity and the resolution at which the
255 proposed parameterized Rao's Q is applied, it might allow finding new insights on the
256 ecological processes acting in a certain ecosystem to shape its diversity. In this paper,
257 the examples provided were based on a single NDVI layer since i) it is a valuable index of
258 vegetation health and ii) it is freely available in the `rasterdiv` package to reproduce the
259 code proposed in this paper (see Appendix S2 for an application at worldwide spatial scale
260 based on the Copernicus Proba-V NDVI freely available in the package). We are aware
261 that NDVI has very limited capacity to track diversity in some habitats like dense forests,
262 because it is saturated at dense vegetation (Mutanga & Skidmore, 2004). From this
263 point of view, imaging spectroscopy offers higher information content, also enabling plant
264 functional trait retrievals (Jetz et al., 2016; Schneider et al., 2019) as well as structural
265 traits by LiDAR data (Schneider et al., 2020). The application of the proposed algorithm
266 to future spaceborne imaging spectroscopy is promising. In other words, the algorithm
267 has been thought to be used with multiple layers, like a whole multispectral image or
268 the most meaningful Principal Components (Peres-Neto et al., 2005), or land use classes
269 probabilities derived from fuzzy set theory (Rocchini & Ricotta, 2007; Feoli, 2018). This
270 is even one of the major advantages of the Rao's Q metric which allows considering both
271 abundance and distance among pixel values, thus being applicable to any continuous
272 raster layer, or to any matrix combination, even in a multiple spectral system.

273 Creating a unique "umbrella" under which all of the potential metrics of diversity can
274 be used is highly beneficial for e.g. monitoring the variation in time of biological systems
275 considering two major axes: i) the α parameter in Equation 5 providing information
276 about the type of diversity at time t_0 , ii) the temporal dimension from time t_0 to time t_n
277 given the same α parameter. For the future, exploring such temporal dimension would

278 allow gathering information of ecosystem changes in different diversity types at a glance.

279 Moreover, generalized entropy allows us to characterize the dimensionality of diversity
280 (*sensu* Stevens & Tello, 2014) of different habitats/ecosystems. Those areas with a higher
281 diversity dimensionality, namely a higher variability into the diversity spectrum would
282 need a generalized measure to be fully undertaken. On the contrary, ecosystems with a
283 lower dimensionality would have a lower difference among the different diversity measures
284 with a flat curve of the diversity spectrum (Nakamura et al., 2020).

285 From a functional point of view, when all indices of diversity are highly correlated to
286 each other (low dimensionality), it is expected that the ecological processes underlying
287 diversity are just a few. On the contrary, with a lower correlation among indices (higher
288 dimensionality) there might be a higher number of axes of variation coming out from
289 different processes shaping ecological heterogeneity in space (Stevens & Tello, 2014).

290 There might be the possibility that a completely random matrix produces a pattern
291 of diversity (Type I error). On the other side, a structured matrix could produce a very
292 low diversity pattern (Type II error, Gotelli (2000)). In both cases, the parametric Rao's
293 Q could allow to determine, thanks to the use of a continuum of diversities, i) why a
294 diversity pattern is still produced even in case of a random matrix, and ii) why a certain
295 landscape shows a very low diversity in a certain point of the whole diversity spectrum.
296 With point descriptors of diversity such inference cannot be done since the investigation
297 is limited to a small window of the entire diversity spectrum, by basically relying on a
298 single final number. In other words, the commonly asked question about what is the
299 index which best describes diversity has no certain answer (Gorelick, 2011). Hence, the
300 use of a trend of diversities will lead to the comprehension of hidden parts of the whole
301 diversity dimensionality.

302 Furthermore, it is expected that the ecological processes shaping diversity should act
303 at defined spatial scales (Borcard & Legendre, 2002). Hence, different diversity types of
304 the whole dimensionality spectrum are expected to show scale dependent patterns, being
305 apparent only at certain scales and not at some others. The use of a continuum allows
306 measuring the different diversity types altogether in a single step. Changing the extent
307 of analysis by different moving windows would then allow to encompass different spatial
308 structures at different scales.

309 While geographic gradients of diversity over space are complex to catch in their very
310 nature, biodiversity measurement has mainly relied in the past on few formulas which
311 represented an hegemony (Stevens et al., 2013). In this paper, we demonstrated that
312 diversity is actually multifaceted and should be necessarily approached through a gener-
313 alized approach. Furthermore, the proposed generalized parametric Rao's Q index might
314 be profitably used to plot multitemporal trends (see e.g. Dornelas et al., 2014) of diver-
315 sity metrics and discover previously imperceptible differences when making use of single
316 metrics (Figure 4).

317 **5 Conclusion**

318 In order to unfold the dimensionality of diversity methods to directly account for several
319 aspects of diversity at a time are needed. From this point of view, generalized entropy
320 undoubtedly represents a powerful approach for mapping the diversity continuum.

321 Metrics grounded in Information Theory ensure to make use of relative abundance of
322 pixel values given the same richness in the moving window of analysis. However, distance
323 metrics allow to also account for the relative dispersion in the spectral space of the cloud
324 of pixels in a certain area (Laliberté et al., 2020). The proposed parameterization of the

325 Rao's Q explicitly considers the dispersion of pixel values in a spectral space (and their
326 relative abundance) by allowing catching the whole dimensionality of diversity.

327 **6 Data availability**

328 The code and the data used in this paper are based on completely Free and Open Source
329 Software, and they are available at the CRAN repository of the R package `rasterdiv`:
330 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv>.

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Figure 1: Grounding theory of this paper. Diversity measures can encompass abundance-based as well as abundance-distance-based metrics (yellow and green boxes, respectively). Abundance-distance-based metrics allow multiple layers to be used. The black lines represent the theoretical flow of this paper, with the thickness representing the complexity of each index, starting from Shannon's Information Theory (point descriptor) to Rényi's H_α (generalized entropy), which do not make use of distance. Distance enters the Rao's Q formula, but this is still a point descriptor of diversity. Finally, parametric Rao's Q_α comprises the use of distances and the generalized entropy concept. The red arrows represent the properties of the Rao's Q_α : i) it is grounded in Information Theory starting from Shannon's H , ii) it is a generalized entropy like the Rényi H_α , and iii) it makes use of distances like the Rao's Q .

Figure 2: Maps showing NDVI, the Rao's Q Index, native plant species richness for the ecoregions of California. The NDVI values shown in the top-left box (100 m resolution) were derived from the ESA Copernicus Sentinel-2 dataset, processed with Google Earth Engine and range between -0.26 (red) and 0.99 (dark green). The Rao's Q indices in the top-right boxes were calculated from the NDVI map using $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$ and a moving window of 9x9 pixels. Rao's Q higher values represent pixels whose surrounding NDVI values are more "diverse" than pixels with lower Rao's Q values. The bottom map, reporting the pixels' potential native plant species richness (resolution: 810 m), was derived summing the binary potential distribution ranges of 5,222 native plant species modelled by Thornhill et al. (2017). Species richness ranges between 134 (red) to 1029 (green) species per pixel (1 km²). Five ecoregions were labelled in the NDVI map and discussed in the main text: Coast range (CR), Klamath Mountains (KM), Cascades (CAS), California Central Valley (CCV) and Mohave basin and range (MBR). A mask with water bodies was added to the maps. Refer to the main text for additional information.

Figure 3: Boxplot showing the values distribution of NDVI, the parametric Rao's Q (with $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$) and plant species richness. The Rao's Q index matched native plant species diversity in those ecoregions characterized by a lower human impact, such as Cascades (CAS), Klamath Mountains (KM), Coast range (CR), Mohave basin and range (MBR). On the other hand, Rao's Q performed poorly when compared with native plant species richness in agricultural and developed lands with a high productivity (i.e., high NDVI) and heterogeneity (California Central Valley, CCV). See also Figure 2 and the main text for additional information.

Figure 4: A theoretical example of the power of using generalized entropy for monitoring purposes. Given a landscape at times t_0 (pink) and t_n (blue), calculating generalized entropy will allow the formation of a graph showing the continuum of Rao's Q values observed over a range of values for α . The same landscape in different times might show an abrupt change (e.g., a catastrophic event) with an apparent diversity decrease (top). In this case, point descriptors (e.g., single α values) of diversity may be sufficient to describe this pattern. When the change in diversity is subtle (bottom), using a point descriptor might fail to detect it but it becomes manifest in the continuum of diversities based on generalized entropy. The complete code for reproducing this theoretical example is available in Appendix S3.